

Use of CDEs Supports the NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy

Common data elements (CDEs) help researchers share and combine datasets, meet funding requirements, and save time. [Learn More...](#)

[Search All CDEs](#) [Search NIH-Endorsed CDEs](#) [Search Forms](#)

Search by topic, keyword, or organization

CDEs in the Repository have been submitted by NIH recognized bodies.

 [Explore](#) [Learn](#) [Submit](#)

▼

Explore CDEs and Forms

A **Common Data Element (CDE)** is a standardized, precisely defined question, paired with a set of allowable responses, used systematically across different sites, studies, or clinical trials to ensure consistent data collection.

Multiple CDEs (from one or more Collections) can be curated into **Forms**. Forms in the Repository might be original, or might recreate the format of real-world data collection instruments or case report forms.

NIH has endorsed collections of CDEs that meet established criteria. **NIH-endorsed CDEs** are designated with a gold ribbon.

[Browse NIH-Endorsed CDEs](#) [Browse All CDEs](#) [Browse Forms](#)

